

indicated that the population was significantly different from populations of biotypes 1, 2, and 3. We categorized the grass-infesting population as a primitive, non-virulent *N. lugens* biotype. To further ascertain its taxonomic status, we studied its cytology and compared it with that of the field population of rice-infesting BPH.

The testicular cells of brachypters sampled from grass and rice hosts were examined using the standard cytological techniques for planthoppers (Table 1).

The two BPH populations differed significantly in frequency of actively dividing cells or meiocytes, meiotic index, width of interphase nuclei, length and width of leptotene nuclei, lengths of telophase I clumps, and sperm lengths, but not in other cellular features (Table 1). Male rice BPH undergo more frequent meioses and yield more but shorter spermatozoa than the male of the grass-infesting BPH.

Substantial variation between BPH populations was observed during the pachytene stage (Table 2). Karyotypes and idiograms of the two BPH populations show clear individual chromosomes of different relative mean lengths (rml) (Fig. 1, 2). For instance, the chromosome with the nucleolus organizing region (site of ribosomal RNA synthesis) measured 47.20 mm for the rice BPH vs 20.75 mm for the grass-infesting BPH. The rice BPH generally had longer chromosomes (rml 20.40 to 63.30 mm) than the grass-infesting BPH (rml 10.25 to 40.75 mm). The nucleolar organelle of the rice BPH was either a darkly stained body or two fused nucleoli, whereas that of the grass-infesting BPH was simply a densely stained ovoid body.

Chromosomal behavior was similar for both populations, except that the intensive coiling of the rice BPH chromosomes during diakinesis resulted in shorter and more highly heterochromatic chromosomes than those of the grass-infesting

Table 2. Variations in the mean relative lengths of pachytene chromosomes of BPH populations infesting rice and grass hosts, IRRI, 1982-83.

Autosome no.	Mean relative length (mm) of pachytene chromosomes				Difference ^a
	Grass-infesting BPH		Rice-infesting BPH		
	\bar{x}	SEM	\bar{x}	SEM	
1	10.0	0.00	18.0	1.61	- 8.0**
2	10.3	0.21	22.3	1.26	-12.0**
3	10.4	0.27	25.3	1.17	-14.9**
4	10.4	0.27	28.2	1.89	-17.8**
5	11.0	0.36	29.5	1.56	-18.5**
6	20.0	0.00	30.7	1.43	-10.7**
7	20.3	0.21	32.7	1.84	-12.4**
8	20.5	0.22	35.3	0.80	-14.8**
9	21.0	0.06	38.4	1.87	-17.4**
10	30.0	0.00	40.3	1.82	-10.3**
11	30.0	0.00	42.7	1.71	-12.7**
12	30.2	0.17	47.5	2.20	-17.3**
13	30.8	0.17	51.2	2.33	-20.4**
14	40.0	0.00	54.5	2.79	-14.5**
15	40.7	0.21	64.2	2.31	-23.5**

^a ** = significant at 1% level, av of 6 samples.

Table 3. Variations in the means of absolute chromosome length during diakinesis of BPH populations infesting rice and grass hosts, IRRI, 1982-83.

Autosome no.	Absolute chromosome length (μ)				Difference ^a
	Grass-infesting BPH		Rice-infesting BPH		
	\bar{x}	SEM	\bar{x}	SEM	
1	1.6	0.13	1.4	0.07	0.2ns
2	1.9	0.18	1.6	0.07	0.3ns
3	2.1	0.18	1.8	0.06	0.3ns
4	2.3	0.15	2.0	0.00	0.3**
5	2.5	0.17	2.1	0.05	0.4ns
6	2.8	0.17	2.3	0.08	0.5*
7	3.0	0.18	2.4	0.10	0.6*
8	3.2	0.19	2.7	0.08	0.5*
9	3.4	0.20	2.8	0.09	0.6*
10	3.7	0.18	3.0	0.10	0.7**
11	3.9	0.18	3.4	0.12	0.5*
12	4.4	0.23	3.5	0.13	0.9**
13	4.8	0.25	3.7	0.08	1.1**
14	5.4	0.28	4.2	0.12	1.2**
Sex chromosomes	3.8	0.12	3.1	0.15	0.7**

^a ns = no significant difference, * = significant at 5% level, ** = significant at 1% level, av of 15 samples.

BPH (Table 3).

Those cytological criteria may be used as complementary taxonomic indices for characterizing and differentiating grass-infesting BPH from rice BPH. These observations further confirm the uniqueness of the grass-infesting population and justifi-

fy its categorization as an additional *N. lugens* variant or biotype. Thus, despite their taxonomic similarities, a distinct cytological incongruity and a certain degree of genetic isolation between the two *N. lugens* populations can be inferred. □

Efficacy of nursery protection and seedling root dip for gall midge control

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In Goa, gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* is a serious insect problem, especially in kharif. We attempted to develop an inexpensive control.

In 1981 kharif, we used susceptible Jaya to test eight treatments: a) carbo-

furan alone (1.25 kg ai/ha), b) 500 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, c) 1,000 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, d) 1,500 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, e) 2,000 kg neem cake/ha + carbofuran, f) treatment a + chlorpyrifos 0.02% seedling root dip

in 1% urea solution for 3 h at planting, g) treatment a + chlorpyrifos 0.02% seedling root dip for 12 h at planting, and h) control. Neem cake and carbofuran granules were applied in the nursery at 20 days after sowing (DS) and water was impounded until seedlings were pulled and planted at 27 DS.

The comparative efficacy of different treatments was rated by GM damage and the grain yield (see table).

The carbofuran nursery treatment + chlorpyrifos seedling root dip was superior to nursery treatments with carbofuran alone or a combination of carbofuran and neem cake for controlling GM and encouraging higher grain yield. Irrespective of the combination of nursery treatments, neither carbofuran alone nor in combina-

Effect of different treatments on GM damage and rice grain yield at 50 DT.^a

Treatment	Gall midge damage (%)	Productive tillers/hill	Grain yield (t/ha)
Carbofuran 1.25 kg ai/ha	35 c	5.4 b	2.7 d
Carbofuran + 500 kg NC/ha	34 c	5.4 b	2.6 d
Carbofuran + 1000 kg NC/ha	35 c	5.4 b	2.5 d
Carbofuran + 1500 kg NC/ha	41 c	5.3 b	2.9 c
Carbofuran + 2000 kg NC/ha	35 c	5.6 b	2.8 cd
Carbofuran + RD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution for 3 h at planting	22 b	6.8 a	3.8 b
Carbofuran + RD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h at planting	8 a	6.9 a	4.0 a
Control	42 c	4.0 c	2.1 c

^aIn a column, data with common letters are not significantly different at 5% level. NC = neem cake, DT = days after transplanting, RD = root dip.

tion with neem cake, even at 2,000 kg neem cake/ha, affected GM. Nursery treatment with carbofuran at 1.25 kg ai/ha +

chlorpyrifos 0.02% seedling root dip for 12 h before planting provided best and most economic control. □

Characterization of the brown planthopper population on IR42 in North Sumatra, Indonesia

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Rice resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) is an important component in the integrated management of BPH in Indonesia. However, new BPH biotypes that defeated resistance traits of some rice varieties have evolved.

Drastic shifts of BPH biotypes that have occurred in North Sumatra, a BPH epidemic area in Indonesia, have followed shifts in rice varieties planted. Biotype 2 developed in 1977 on IR26, which has the *bph 1* gene. Until 1981, that biotype was effectively suppressed by IR36, which has the *bph 2* gene. However, recently introduced IR42 with the *bph 2* gene was damaged by a new biotype.

We compared the BPH population collected from IR42 in North Sumatra (hereafter the N. S. population) with that of the known biotypes by two honeydew tests: one with filter paper and one with parafilm envelopes. The N. S. population was reared for about 20 successive generations on IR42 at the Bogor Food Crops Research Institute. Biotypes 1, 2, and 3 have been maintained as isolated inbred

Relative amounts of honeydew excreted by 4 BPH biotypes on 7 rice varieties, 1983.^a

Variety	Honeydew ^a			N.S. ^b
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3	
TN1	19.0	18.5	17.7	10.2
Pelita I/1	21.8	15.6	16.5	10.4
IR26	3.8	14.9	2.6	4.1
Cisadane	±	±	4.8	3.6
IR42	±	±	3.6	11.1
IR36	±	±	±	2.1
IR56	±	±	±	±

^a Five adult females were confined on a plant at about 30 days after transplanting for 22 hours at room temperature. Values indicate the areas of water blue filter paper impregnated with honeydew in cm² (av of 3 replications). Excretion of only a small number of droplets is indicated by ±. ^bNorth Sumatra population.

populations on Pelita I/1, Mudgo, and ASD7, respectively, since 1977.

Table 1 shows estimates by the filter paper method of the relative amounts of honeydew excreted by adult females of the three biotypes and the N. S. on selected rice varieties. The N. S. population was differentiated from biotype 2 by a poor ability to feed on IR26, and from biotypes 1 and 3 by an improved ability to feed on IR42 (see table). N. S. feeding characteristics were further confirmed by the parafilm envelope method and compared to those of BPH biotype 3. The N. S. population excreted as much honeydew on *bph 2*-resistant varieties ASD7 and IR42 as on susceptible variety Pelita I/1, but excreted strikingly less honeydew on

Means and 95% confidential ranges of the amount of honeydew excreted by adult females of the N. S. population and biotype 3 at Bogor on 8 rice varieties at about 45 days after transplanting. About 20 insects were used for each variety, 1983.

Babawee, IR56, Mudgo, Cisadane, and IR36 (see figure). This indicated that the N. S. population belongs to biotype 3, which has specific ability to feed on *bph 2*-resistant varieties.

However, the N. S. population has a significantly higher ability to feed on IR42 than does biotype 3 at Bogor. N. S. insects excreted nearly 30 mg honeydew/female per d, while those from the biotype 3 culture excreted only 5 mg (see figure). These different BPH responses seem to indicate that there are different genetic factor(s) in each host variety that cause a distinct reaction to IR42 on each biotypic population, although IR42 and ASD7 have been said to possess the same *bph 2* gene. □